

University of Trás-os-Montes and Alto Douro

Risk assessment of heavy precipitation events in Portugal

– Appendices –

Doctorate in Applied Physical Sciences

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Appendix A:

**Studies on Heavy Precipitation in Portugal: A
Systematic Review**

Table A1. PRISMA 2020 for the abstract checklist.

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Reported (Yes/No)
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Yes
BACKGROUND			
Objectives	2	Provide an explicit statement of the main objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Yes
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	3	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review.	Yes
Information sources	4	Specify the information sources (e.g. databases, registers) used to identify studies and the date when each was last searched.	Yes
Risk of bias	5	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies.	Yes
Synthesis of results	6	Specify the methods used to present and synthesise results.	Yes
RESULTS			
Included studies	7	Give the total number of included studies and participants and summarise relevant characteristics of studies.	Yes
Synthesis of results	8	Present results for main outcomes, preferably indicating the number of included studies and participants for each. If meta-analysis was done, report the summary estimate and confidence/credible interval. If comparing groups, indicate the direction of the effect (i.e. which group is favoured).	Yes
DISCUSSION			
Limitations of evidence	9	Provide a brief summary of the limitations of the evidence included in the review (e.g. study risk of bias, inconsistency and imprecision).	Yes
Interpretation	10	Provide a general interpretation of the results and important implications.	Yes
OTHER			
Funding	11	Specify the primary source of funding for the review.	Yes
Registration	12	Provide the register name and registration number.	No

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Table A2. PRISMA 2020 checklist.

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Page 9
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	Table A1
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	Section 2.1
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Section 2.1
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	Section 2.2.1.1
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	Section 2.2.1.2
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	Section 2.2.1.3
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Section 2.2.2
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Section 2.2.2
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	Section 2.2.2
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	Section 2.2.2
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Section 2.2.2
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	Section 2.2.2
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item #5)).	Section 2.2.2
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	Section 2.2.2

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	Section 2.2.2
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	Section 2.2.2
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	Section 2.2.2
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	Section 2.2.2
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	Section 2.2.2
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	Section 2.2.2
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	Section 2.3.1
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	Section 2.2.2
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	Section 2.3.2
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	N/A
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	Section 2.3.2
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	N/A
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	Section 2.3.2
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	Section 2.3.2
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	Section 2.3.2
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	N/A
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	Section 2.3.2
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	Section 2.4
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	Section 2.4 and 2.5

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Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	Section 2.4 and 2.5
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	Section 2.5
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	N/A
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	N/A
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	N/A
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	Page 41, Funding section (Original Article)
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	Page 20, Conflicts of Interest section (Original Article)
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	Page 20; Data Availability Statement section (Original Article)

Table A3. Selection criteria applied on research platforms.

Scopus	Web of Science (WoS)
Limited to subject area:	Limited to web of science categories:
Earth and Planetary Sciences; Environmental Science; Agricultural and Biological Sciences	Environmental Sciences; Geosciences Multidisciplinary; Meteorology Atmospheric Sciences; Geography Physical; Environmental Studies; Geography; Agriculture Multidisciplinary
Limited to document type:	Limited to document type:
Article; Review	Article; Review
Limited to language:	Limited to language:
English	English
Limited to keyword	Limited to citation topics meso
Portugal; Floods; Flooding Climate Change; Extreme Event; Risk Assessment; Lisboa [Portugal]; Flood; Rain; Rainfall; Numerical Model; Runoff; Vulnerability; Storms; Precipitation Intensity; Precipitation (climatology); Lisbon; Tagus Estuary; Seasonal Variation; Extreme Precipitation; Coimbra [Portugal]; Flood Damage; Precipitation (meteorology); Aveiro [Portugal]; Weather Forecasting; Ria De Aveiro; Faro [Portugal]; Precipitation; Landslide; Climate Effect; Precipitation Assessment; North Atlantic Oscillation; Landslides; Climate Modeling; Atlantic Ocean (North); Algarve; Extreme Rainfall; Regional Climate; Climate Variation; Weather; Rainfall-runoff Modeling; Porto [Portugal]; Numerical Models; Extreme Weather Events; Atmospheric Pressure; Agriculture	Oceanography, Meteorology & Atmospheric Sciences; Climate Change; Environmental Sciences
	Limited to citation topics micro
	Evapotranspiration; Climate Change Adaptation; Enso; Tropical Cyclones; Stormwater; Clouds

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Table A4. Articles selected for the analysis of observed changes and future projections.

Title	Reference
Trends in extreme precipitation indices derived from a daily rainfall database for the South of Portugal	(Costa and Soares, 2009)
Indices of precipitation extremes in Southern Portugal-a geostatistical approach	(R. Durão et al., 2009)
Spatial-temporal dynamics of precipitation extremes in southern Portugal: A geostatistical assessment study	(R. M. Durão et al., 2010)
Trends in frequency indices of daily precipitation over the Iberian Peninsula during the last century	(Gallego et al., 2011)
Climate change scenarios for precipitation extremes in Portugal	(Costa et al., 2012)
Precipitation variability in Northern Portugal: Data homogeneity assessment and trends in extreme precipitation indices	(M. Santos and Fragoso, 2013)
Recent changes in daily precipitation and surface air temperature extremes in mainland Portugal, in the period 1941-2007	(M. I. P. De Lima, Santo, et al., 2013)
Recent precipitation variability over 67 years in mainland Portugal	(M. I. P. De Lima, Espírito Santo, et al., 2013)
A ranking of high-resolution daily precipitation extreme events for the Iberian Peninsula	(Ramos, Trigo, et al., 2014)
Seasonal changes in daily precipitation extremes in mainland Portugal from 1941 to 2007	(Espírito-Santo et al., 2014)
Trends and correlations in annual extreme precipitation indices for mainland Portugal, 1941-2007	(M. I. P. De Lima et al., 2015)
Climate change and the Portuguese precipitation: ENSEMBLES regional climate models results	(P. M. M. Soares et al., 2015)
Recent trends of extreme precipitation indices in the Iberian Peninsula using observations and WRF model results	(Bartolomeu et al., 2016)
Regionalization and susceptibility assessment to daily precipitation extremes in mainland Portugal	(M. Santos, Fragoso, et al., 2017)
Ranking of multi-day extreme precipitation events over the Iberian Peninsula	(Ramos et al., 2017)
Future precipitation in Portugal: high-resolution projections using WRF model and EURO-CORDEX multi-model ensembles	(P. M. M. Soares et al., 2017)
Recent and future changes of precipitation extremes in mainland Portugal	(M. Santos et al., 2019)
Long-Term Rainfall Trends and Their Variability in Mainland Portugal in the Last 106 Years	(Portela et al., 2020)
Climate-Change Adaptation Framework for Multiple Urban Areas in Northern Portugal	(Coelho et al., 2020)
Climate Change Trends in a European Coastal Metropolitan Area: Rainfall, Temperature, and Extreme Events (1864–2021)	(Espinosa et al., 2022)
A multi-variable constrained ensemble of regional climate projections under multi-scenarios for Portugal – Part I: An overview of impacts on means and extremes	(D. C. A. Lima et al., 2023)
Exposure of Portuguese viticulture to weather extremes under climate change	(Fonseca et al., 2023)
The probability of unprecedented high rainfall in wine regions of northern Portugal	(Sanderson et al., 2023)

Table A5. Articles selected for the analysis of large-scale atmospheric patterns.

Title	Reference
Circulation weather types and their influence on the precipitation regime in Portugal	(R. M. Trigo and DaCamara, 2000)
Links between circulation and changes in the characteristics of Iberian rainfall	(Goodess and Jones, 2002)
The Influence of the North Atlantic Oscillation on rainfall triggering of landslides near Lisbon	(R. M. Trigo et al., 2005)
Classification of daily abundant rainfall patterns and associated large-scale atmospheric circulation types in Southern Portugal	(Fragoso and Tildes Gomes, 2008)
Circulation types and extreme precipitation days in the Iberian Peninsula in the transition seasons: Spatial links and temporal changes	(Fernández-Montes et al., 2014)
Historical damaging flood records for 1871-2011 in Northern Portugal and underlying atmospheric forcings	(M. Santos et al., 2015)
Daily precipitation extreme events in the Iberian Peninsula and its association with atmospheric rivers	(Ramos et al., 2015)
The deadliest storm of the 20th century striking Portugal: Flood impacts and atmospheric circulation	(R. M. Trigo et al., 2016)
Atmospheric driving mechanisms of flash floods in Portugal	(M. Santos, Santos, et al., 2017)
A centennial catalogue of hydro-geomorphological events and their atmospheric forcing	(S. Pereira et al., 2018)
Extreme Precipitation Events in Summer in the Iberian Peninsula and Its Relationship With Atmospheric Rivers	(Ramos et al., 2018)
Earlier awareness of extreme winter precipitation across the western Iberian Peninsula	(Lavers et al., 2018)
Analysis of the 1 November 2015 heavy rainfall episode in Algarve by using weather radar and rain gauge data	(Barbosa et al., 2018)
Meteorological driving mechanisms and human impacts of the February 1979 extreme hydro-geomorphological event in Western Iberia	(Rebelo et al., 2018)
Consecutive extratropical cyclones daniel, elsa and fabien, and their impact on the hydrological cycle of mainland portugal	(Stojanovic et al., 2021)
Sub-Hourly Precipitation Extremes in Mainland Portugal and Their Driving Mechanisms	(J. A. Santos and Belo-Pereira, 2022)
Dynamic and Thermodynamic Drivers of Severe Sub-Hourly Precipitation Events in Mainland Portugal	(Cruz et al., 2023)

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Table A6. Articles selected for the evaluation of different databases and the performance of Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) models.

Title	Reference
Numerical simulation of a heavy rainfall event over Portugal using mesoscale model	(Ramos et al., 2012)
Simulation of a persistent medium-term precipitation event over the western Iberian Peninsula	(S. C. Pereira et al., 2013)
On the influence of physical parameterisations and domains configuration in the simulation of an extreme precipitation event	(J. A. Ferreira et al., 2014)
On the inclusion of GPS precipitable water vapour in the nowcasting of rainfall	(Benevides et al., 2015)
Uncertainty in different precipitation products in the case of two atmospheric river events	(Ramos et al., 2021)

Table A7. Articles selected for the analysis of other extreme events.

Title	Reference
Relationship between convective precipitation and cloud-to-ground lightning in the Iberian Peninsula	(Soriano et al., 2001)
Tornadoes in Portugal	(Leitão, 2003)
Cloud-to-ground lightning in Portugal: Patterns and dynamical forcing	(J. A. Santos et al., 2012)
Forcing factors of cloud-to-ground lightning over Iberia: Regional-scale assessments	(J. A. Santos, Reis, et al., 2013)
Statistical-dynamical modelling of the cloud-to-ground lightning activity in Portugal	(J. F. Sousa et al., 2013)
A long-lived tornado on 7 December 2010 in mainland Portugal	(Belo-Pereira et al., 2017)
A comprehensive analysis of hail events in Portugal: Climatology and consistency with atmospheric circulation	(J. A. Santos and Belo-Pereira, 2019)
Tornadoes in Portugal: An overview	(Leitão and Pinto, 2020)
ECMWF Lightning Forecast in Mainland Portugal during Four Fire Seasons	(Campos et al., 2024)

Table A8. Summary of the number of studies conducted by country.

Countries	Number of studies
Portugal	46
Spain	3
United Kingdom	4
Brazil	1

Appendix B:

**Dynamic and Thermodynamic Drivers of Severe Sub-
Hourly Precipitation Events in Mainland Portugal**

Table B1. List of the selected 34 weather stations (WS) in mainland Portugal. Their codes and names are shown. The corresponding percentages of missing values on the daily timescale precipitation over the recording period are also provided.

Code	Weather station name	Nb. of days with data	Missing data (%)
541	Sines Monte	8185	3
604	Geres Carris	7399	12
566	Vila Real	8388	0
545	Porto Pedras Rubras	7781	7
707	Coimbra	8363	0
568	Penhas Douradas	7979	5
557	Évora	8384	0
579	Lisboa Gago Coutinho	7971	5
535	Lisboa Geofísico	7810	7
551	Viana do Castelo	8134	3
554	Faro Aeroporto	7488	11
560	Viseu CC	8177	3
562	Beja	7805	7
570	Castelo Branco	7840	7
571	Portalegre	8007	5
575	Bragança	7632	9
577	Odemira S. Teotónio	6805	19
611	Montalegre	6921	18
616	Chaves Aeródromo	7472	11
619	Cabril	7180	15
632	Mirandela	6947	17
635	Miranda do Douro	6803	19
637	Mogadouro	7087	16
683	Guarda	7159	15
685	Nelas	7342	13
697	Lousã Aeródromo	7184	14
705	Anadia	7044	16
803	Zebreira	7072	16
812	Alvega	7213	14
824	Avis Benavila	7013	17
835	Elvas	7715	8
837	Estremoz	6775	19
867	Castro Marim	6785	19
878	Portimão Aeródromo	7294	13

Appendix B:Dynamic and Thermodynamic Drivers of Severe Sub-Hourly Precipitation Events in Mainland Portugal

Table B2. Number and percentage of events recorded in each station and by precipitation class.

Weather Station	Composites	Nb. of Events	Pct. of Events
Viana do Castelo (VC)	C0	6248	65.4
	C1	2035	21.3
	C2	1215	12.7
	C3	60	0.6
Castelo Branco (CB)	C0	6153	72.8
	C1	1391	16.5
	C2	853	10.1
	C3	51	0.6
Faro (F)	C0	5747	76.2
	C1	1063	14.1
	C2	659	8.7
	C3	75	1.0

Figure B1. Composites of hourly anomalies of MSLP (in hPa) (shading) and Z500 (in gpm) (contours lines represented in green, with a spacing of 25 gpm) for (a,b,c) C1, (d,e,f) C2, and (g,h,i) C3.

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Dynamic and Thermodynamic Drivers of Severe Sub-Hourly Precipitation Events in Mainland Portugal

Figure B2. Hourly composites of total column water vapour (TCWV, shading in mm) for precipitation classes (a,b,c) C0, (d,e,f) C1, (g,h,i) C2, and (j,k,l) C3 in each WS (VC, CB, and F).

Figure B3. Composites of hourly anomalies of temperature anomaly (in °C) for precipitation class C3 (SHHP events), at different vertical levels, and for (a) VC, (b) CB, and (c) F.

Figure B4. (a) Meridional and (b) zonal cross-sections of relative vorticity composites of hourly anomalies (shading in s^{-1}) and omega-vertical velocity (contours in $Pa s^{-1}$, positive/negative values in solid/dashed lines) for class C3 and CB.

Figure B5. (a) Meridional and (b) zonal cross-sections of relative vorticity composites of hourly anomalies (shading in s^{-1}) and omega-vertical velocity (contours in $Pa s^{-1}$, positive/negative values in solid/dashed lines) for class C3 and F.

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Figure B6. Hourly composites of MSLP (shading in hPa) and position of meridional and zonal cross-sections (white dashed lines) for precipitation class C3 (SHHP events), for (a) VC, (b) CB, and (c) F.

Figure B7. Hourly composites of CAPE (shading in J kg^{-1}) and Total-Totals index (blue contours in $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 2°C spacing), for (a,b,c) C0, (d,e,f) C1, (g,h,i) C2 (j,k,l), and C3 in each WS (VC, CB, and F).

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Figure B8. Hourly composites of convective inhibition (CIN, shading in J kg^{-1}) for precipitation classes (a,b,c) C0, (d,e,f) C1, (g,h,i) C2, and (j,k,l) C3 in each WS (VC, CB, and F).

Figure B9. Hourly composites of K-index (shading in °C) for (a,b,c) C0, (d,e,f) C1, (g,h,i) C2 (j,k,l), and C3 in each WS (VC, CB, and F).

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Figure B10. Hourly composites of total column cloud liquid water, TCCLW (shading in g m^{-2}) for precipitation classes (a,b,c) C1, (d,e,f) C2, and (g,h,i) C3 in each WS (VC, CB, and F).

Figure B11. Boxplots of (a) CAPE (in J kg^{-1}), (b) CIN (in J kg^{-1}), (c) K-index (in $^{\circ}\text{C}$), (d) TT-index (in $^{\circ}\text{C}$), (e) TCWV (in mm), and (f) vertical velocity 700 hPa (in Pa s^{-1}) for precipitation events C3 in each WS (VC, CB, and F).

Appendix C:

**Spatial-Temporal Variability of Hourly Precipitation
Extremes in Portugal: Two Case Studies in Major Wine-
Growing Regions**

Table C1. List of the selected 71 surface weather stations (WS) in mainland Portugal: code, weather station name, latitude (°N), longitude (°W), altitude (meters above mean sea level), the start and end years of the recorded data by the surface weather station and, the corresponding percentages of missing data in the observed 10-minute precipitation period of 2000–2022 (23 years). Stations highlighted in their codes with * and bold represent the final code after joining data from other stations (highlighted in italic). Stations marked with ‘#’ represent the selected surface weather stations to characterise the Douro winemaking region. Stations marked with ‘+’ represent the selected surface weather stations to characterise the Alentejo winemaking region.

Cod e	Weather Station name	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)	Altitude (m)	Start year	End year	Missing data 2000 – 2022 (%)
531	Cabo Carvoeiro	39.361	9.406	32	2000	2022	15
533	Sagres	37.012	8.949	25	2000	2022	8
535*	Lisboa Geofísico	38.719	9.149	77	2000	2022	2
579	<i>Lisboa Gago Coutinho</i>	38.766	9.128	104	2000	2022	
762	<i>Lisboa Ajuda</i>	38.710	9.183	69	2019	2022	
541*	Sines Monte	37.954	8.838	103	2000	2022	3
542	<i>Sines Cabo</i>	37.957	8.887	19	2009	2014	
543*	Viana do Castelo	41.706	8.802	16	2000	2006	2
551	<i>Viana do Castelo</i>	41.648	8.804	48	2006	2022	
545	Porto Pedras Rubras	41.233	8.681	63	2000	2022	5
546	Porto Serra Pilar	41.138	8.602	93	2009	2022	64
548*	Coimbra Aeródromo	40.156	8.467	170	2000	2022	2
707	<i>Coimbra</i>	40.213	8.455	35	2019	2022	
554*	Faro Aeroporto	37.016	7.971	8	2000	2022	14
555	<i>Faro</i>	37.018	7.921	32	2002	2010	
557*	Évora (+)	38.572	7.906	309	2002	2022	4
558	<i>Évora CC</i>	38.536	7.887	246	2000	2022	
560	Viseu CC	40.714	7.895	636	2000	2022	1
562	Beja (+)	38.024	7.867	246	2000	2022	6
566	Vila Real	41.308	7.740	481	2010	2022	49
567	Vila Real CC (#)	41.274	7.717	561	2000	2022	0
568	Penhas Douradas	40.411	7.558	1380	2000	2022	9
570	Castelo Branco	39.839	7.478	449	2000	2022	3
571	Portalegre (+)	39.294	7.421	597	2000	2022	2
575	Braganca	41.803	6.742	690	2000	2022	5
577*	Odemira S. Teotónio	37.525	8.754	76	2000	2022	10
788	<i>Zambujeira</i>	37.582	8.743	67	2019	2022	
604	Geres Carris	41.750	8.033	1480	2000	2022	20
605	Geres	41.733	8.150	370	2000	2022	20
606	Lamas de Mouro	42.033	8.183	880	2000	2020	31
611	Montalegre	41.822	7.787	1005	2000	2022	11
615	Ponte de Lima	41.763	8.571	40	2000	2022	16
616	Chaves Aeródromo	41.725	7.465	360	2000	2022	2

Appendix C:**Spatial-Temporal Variability of Hourly Precipitation Extremes in Portugal: Two Case Studies in Major Wine-Growing Regions**

Cod e	Weather Station name	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)	Altitude (m)	Start year	End year	Missing data 2000 – 2022 (%)
619	Cabril	41.716	8.016	585	2000	2022	11
622	Braga Merelim	41.575	8.451	65	2000	2022	12
630	Cabeceiras de Basto	41.533	7.966	350	2000	2022	16
632	Mirandela	41.514	7.190	250	2000	2022	10
633	Macedo de Cavaleiros	41.567	6.787	702	2001	2020	29
635	Miranda do Douro	41.498	6.271	693	2000	2020	14
637	Mogadouro	41.333	6.724	644	2000	2022	9
644	Carrazeda de Ansiães (#)	41.233	7.283	715	2002	2022	20
654	Moncorvo (#)	41.189	7.018	600	2002	2022	15
666	Trancoso Bandarra	40.780	7.351	850	2000	2022	21
671	Figueira Castro Rodrigo	40.830	6.940	635	2000	2020	21
683	Guarda	40.528	7.278	1020	2000	2022	10
685	Nelas	40.523	7.855	425	2000	2022	9
687	Covilhã Aeródromo	40.264	7.482	482	2000	2022	20
697	Lousa Aeródromo	40.143	8.244	195	2000	2022	10
704	Dunas de Mira	40.446	8.762	14	2019	2022	83
705	Anadia	40.439	8.440	45	2000	2022	8
713	Figueira da Foz	40.140	8.806	4	2019	2022	83
716	Ansião	39.898	8.410	396	2019	2022	83
718	Leiria	39.781	8.821	45	2019	2022	83
721	São Pedro de Moel	39.764	9.031	40	2019	2022	86
746	Santa Cruz	39.126	9.379	40	2019	2022	87
750	Cabo da Roca	38.782	9.498	141	2019	2022	83
767	Pegões	38.651	8.635	64	2019	2022	83
773	Almada	38.617	9.213	5	2019	2022	83
790	Fóia	37.314	8.596	895	2019	2022	85
800	Sabugal	40.339	7.036	858	2000	2022	13
803	Zebreira	39.866	7.016	375	2000	2022	12
806	Proença-a-Nova	39.728	7.870	379	2000	2020	21
812	Alvega	39.461	8.026	51	2000	2022	9
824	Avis Benavila	39.106	7.877	150	2000	2022	10
835	Elvas	38.889	7.140	208	2000	2022	5
837	Estremoz (+)	38.862	7.512	366	2000	2022	12
863	Mértola Vale Formoso	37.757	7.551	190	2000	2022	7
865	Alcoutim Martim	37.437	7.768	290	2000	2022	16
867	Castro Marim	37.229	7.425	5	2000	2022	4
868	Almodôvar	37.400	8.083	400	2000	2016	52
878	Portimão Aeródromo	37.147	8.583	14	2000	2022	6

Table C2. Results of the absolute homogeneity tests and classification of the daily series for the Pettitt (P), SNHT (Standard Normal Homogeneity Test), Buishand and Von Neumann homogeneity hypothesis. The time series were classified as “Useful”, if they did not fail any homogeneity test, “Potentially useful”, if failed only one homogeneity test; and the * represents the series in which the trend was removed. Results of the 95, 99, 99.5 and 99.9th percentiles of hourly precipitation for each station, italic values represent yellow warnings ($10 \leq I < 20 \text{ mm h}^{-1}$) and **bold** values represent orange-red warnings ($I \geq 20 \text{ mm h}^{-1}$).

Code	Weather Station name	Pettitt	SNHT	Buishand	Von Neumann	Classification	p95 th (mm/h)	p99 th (mm/h)	p99.5 th (mm/h)	p99.9 th (mm/h)
531	Cabo Carvoeiro	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	4.3	8.7	<i>11.4</i>	<i>16.9</i>
533	Sagres	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	4.9	<i>11.1</i>	<i>14.3</i>	24.2
535	Lisboa Geofísico	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	5.8	<i>12.0</i>	<i>15.8</i>	26.7
541	Sines Monte	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	4.4	<i>10.4</i>	<i>15.2</i>	30.3
543	Viana do Castelo	✓	✗	✓	✓	Potentially useful	4.8	9.1	<i>11.6</i>	<i>17.5</i>
545	Porto Pedras Rubras	✓	✗	✓	✓	Potentially useful	5.1	9.9	<i>12.6</i>	20.3
546	Porto Serra Pilar	✓	✓	✓	✗	Potentially useful	4.2	8.3	<i>11.3</i>	<i>16.9</i>
548	Coimbra Aeródromo	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	4.2	8.3	<i>11.1</i>	<i>19.0</i>
554	Faro Aeroporto	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	5.8	<i>12.0</i>	<i>16.0</i>	25.5
557	Évora (+)	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful*	4.9	<i>11.3</i>	<i>15.7</i>	34.9
560	Viseu CC	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	4.6	8.1	9.6	<i>16.2</i>
562	Beja (+)	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful*	4.8	9.7	<i>12.2</i>	22.4
566	Vila Real	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	4.0	6.9	8.7	<i>12.4</i>
567	Vila Real CC (#)	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	3.9	7.1	8.3	<i>12.9</i>
568	Penhas Douradas	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	5.2	9.1	<i>10.8</i>	<i>15.8</i>
570	Castelo Branco	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	4.6	9.1	<i>10.9</i>	20.0
571	Portalegre (+)	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	4.6	8.7	<i>10.5</i>	<i>16.6</i>
575	Braganca	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	3.6	6.6	8.2	<i>13.3</i>
577	Odemira S. Teotónio	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful*	4.5	9.5	<i>12.2</i>	21.4
604	Geres Carris	✓	✓	✓	✗	Potentially useful	5.7	<i>11.0</i>	<i>13.7</i>	21.2
605	Geres	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	4.5	8.2	<i>10.0</i>	<i>15.5</i>
606	Lamas de Mouro	✓	✗	✓	✓	Potentially useful	5.2	8.9	<i>10.6</i>	<i>15.2</i>
611	Montalegre	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful*	4.5	7.8	9.3	<i>13.6</i>
615	Ponte de Lima	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	5.2	9.2	<i>11.1</i>	<i>15.6</i>
616	Chaves Aeródromo	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	3.8	6.7	8.6	<i>13.8</i>
619	Cabril	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	5.4	9.3	<i>10.9</i>	<i>14.5</i>

Appendix C:

Spatial-Temporal Variability of Hourly Precipitation Extremes in Portugal: Two Case Studies in Major Wine-Growing Regions

Code	Weather Station name	Pettitt	SNHT	Buishand	Von Neumann	Classification	p95 th (mm/h)	p99 th (mm/h)	p99.5 th (mm/h)	p99.9 th (mm/h)
622	Braga Merelim	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	5.0	9.3	11.5	17.1
630	Cabeceiras de Basto	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful*	4.7	8.2	9.8	14.3
632	Mirandela	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	3.6	6.5	8.2	14.5
633	Macedo de Cavaleiros	✓	✓	✓	✗	Potentially useful	3.5	6.7	8.4	12.6
635	Miranda do Douro	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	3.4	6.5	8.1	12.8
637	Mogadouro	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful*	3.9	7.3	8.8	14.4
644	Carrazeda de Ansiães (#)	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	4.0	7.1	8.5	13.1
654	Moncorvo (#)	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	3.8	7.4	10.0	18.7
666	Trancoso Bandarra	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	3.8	7.2	8.9	13.6
671	Figueira Castro Rodrigo	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful*	3.8	7.3	9.2	15.9
683	Guarda	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful*	5.1	9.7	12.7	22.0
685	Nelas	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	4.6	8.3	10.4	15.0
687	Covilhã Aeródromo	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	5.7	10.2	12.8	20.6
697	Lousa Aeródromo	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful*	4.0	7.7	9.9	15.3
704	Dunas de Mira	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3.5	7.5	9.5	12.8
705	Anadia	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful*	4.5	8.6	11.0	16.1
713	Figueira da Foz	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3.8	7.5	9.6	13.3
716	Ansião	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3.9	8.0	10.0	14.6
718	Leiria	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3.8	7.6	9.4	16.9
721	São Pedro de Moel	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2.4	6.0	7.6	13.5
746	Santa Cruz	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3.6	7.2	9.4	20.6
750	Cabo da Roca	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2.8	6.7	7.3	15.6
767	Pegões	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4.2	9.1	11.5	14.2
773	Almada	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	4.6	8.9	12.9	18.7
790	Fóia	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2.6	5.5	7.1	9.1
800	Sabugal	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	4.8	8.7	10.7	16.4
803	Zebreira	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	4.3	8.6	11.7	22.1
806	Proença-a-Nova	✓	✓	✓	✗	Potentially useful	5.1	9.9	12.4	18.3
812	Alvega	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	4.3	8.9	10.9	17.1
824	Avis Benavila	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	3.8	8.6	10.9	20.2
835	Elvas	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	4.7	9.1	12.1	19.9
837	Estremoz (+)	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	4.2	8.1	10.4	18.1

Appendix C:
Spatial-Temporal Variability of Hourly Precipitation Extremes in Portugal: Two Case Studies in Major Wine-Growing Regions

Code	Weather Station name	Pettitt	SNHT	Buishand	Von Neumann	Classification	p95 th (mm/h)	p99 th (mm/h)	p99.5 th (mm/h)	p99.9 th (mm/h)
863	Mértola Vale Formoso	✓	✓	✓	✗	Potentially useful*	4.3	9.0	12.1	18.7
865	Alcoutim Martim	✓	✓	✓	✗	Potentially useful	4.7	10.7	14.2	22.8
867	Castro Marim	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful	5.3	11.1	14.5	24.2
868	Almodôvar	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful*	5.0	9.5	11.4	16.7
878	Portimão Aeródromo	✓	✓	✓	✓	Useful*	4.6	10.4	13.9	21.1

Appendix C:**Spatial-Temporal Variability of Hourly Precipitation Extremes in Portugal: Two Case Studies in Major Wine-Growing Regions**

Table C3. Coordinates of the Advanced Lightning Sensors (LS7002) and of the TLP (Total Lightning Processor) system at IPMA headquarters in Lisbon.

Sensors	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)
Bragança	41.855	6.706
Braga	41.551	8.422
Castelo Branco	39.823	7.491
Santa Cruz	39.128	9.380
Olhão	37.025	7.840
Lisbon	38.776	9.126

Table C4. Definition of the thermodynamic indices used in the study.

Thermodynamic indices
<p>K-index (°C): is an indicator of atmospheric instability that includes the 850–500 hPa thermal lapse rate, low-level moisture, and the mid-tropospheric saturation deficit (DeRubertis, 2006).</p> $K = (T_{850 \text{ hPa}} - T_{500 \text{ hPa}}) + Td_{850 \text{ hPa}} - (T_{700 \text{ hPa}} - Td_{700 \text{ hPa}})$ <p>T is the temperature and Td is the dew-point temperature.</p>
<p>Total-Totals index (TT-index, °C): is an indicator of atmospheric instability that includes the 850–500 hPa thermal lapse rate and low-level moisture (Peppler and Lamb, 1989).</p> $TT = (T_{850 \text{ hPa}} - T_{500 \text{ hPa}}) + (Td_{850 \text{ hPa}} - T_{500 \text{ hPa}})$
<p>Convective Inhibition (CIN, J·kg⁻¹): is the network per unit mass required to lift a negatively buoyant air parcel from the surface to the Level of Free Convection (LFC), i.e., the “negative area” under the curve defined by the parcel’s temperature as a function of height (blue area in the Figure S1) (Bluestein and Jain, 1985).</p> $CIN = - \int_{Z_0}^{Z_1} g \left(\frac{\theta_c - \theta_{env}}{\theta_{env}} \right) dz,$ <p>where θ_c is the potential temperature of an air parcel having been lifted from the surface (Z_0) up to the Level of Free Convection (LFC, Z_1), and θ_{env} is the potential temperature of the unsaturated environment.</p>
<p>Convective Availability Potential Energy (CAPE, J·kg⁻¹): is the network per unit mass done by the environment on an air parcel which rises from the LFC to the equilibrium level, i.e., the “positive area” under the curve defined by the parcel’s temperature as a function of height (red area in the Figure S1) (Bluestein and Jain, 1985).</p> $CAPE = \int_{Z_1}^{Z_2} g \left(\frac{\theta_c - \theta_{env}}{\theta_{env}} \right) dz,$ <p>where Z_2 is the equilibrium level.</p> <p>CAPE and CIN can be computed using a surface parcel (the surface-based method). Alternatively, can also be computed using the most unstable parcel, referring to the most unstable level in the lower troposphere (usually the 300 or 350 hPa layer closer to the surface). This method is known as most unstable method and is the one used in ERA5.</p>

Appendix C:

Spatial-Temporal Variability of Hourly Precipitation Extremes in Portugal: Two Case Studies in Major Wine-Growing Regions

Figure C1. Example of a sounding plot on a skew T-log p diagram. The solid line represents the environmental temperature, the dotted line indicates the parcel temperature and the dashed line shows the dew point temperature. The Convective Available Potential Energy (CAPE, “positive area”) area is shaded in red, while the Convective Inhibition (CIN, “negative area”) area is shaded in blue. Figure adapted from Bluestein and Jain (1985).

Figure C2. Spatial distribution of the mean number of precipitation events for a 10-year period for (a–d) $10 \leq I < 20 \text{ mm h}^{-1}$, and (e–h) $I \geq 20 \text{ mm h}^{-1}$ for (a, e) winter, (b, f) spring, (c, g) summer, and (d, h) autumn, derived from sub-hourly precipitation data recorded at 63 surface weather station.

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Spatial-Temporal Variability of Hourly Precipitation Extremes in Portugal: Two Case Studies in Major Wine-Growing Regions

Figure C3. Seasonal histogram of the number of precipitation events identified (grey gradient, left axis) and total percentage (blue gradient, right axis) for yellow, orange, and red warnings (defined by IPMA), for a time lag of (a, c, e) $\Delta t = 3h$, and (b, d, f) $\Delta t = 6h$, for the network of (a, b) 63, (c, d) 3, and (e, f) 4 surface weather stations that characterise the mainland Portugal and Douro, and Alentejo winemaking regions, respectively.

Figure C4. Mean contribution of precipitation to total daily precipitation (in %) for the different seasons and different types of weather warnings (green, yellow, orange and red), for a time lag of (a) $\Delta t = 1h$, (b) $\Delta t = 3h$, and (c) $\Delta t = 6h$, derived from sub-hourly precipitation data recorded at 63 surface weather stations.

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Figure C5. (a–h) ERA5 reanalysis data for 250 hPa temperature ($T_{250 \text{ hPa}}$) (in $^\circ\text{C}$, shading colours), and 250 hPa geopotential height ($Z_{250 \text{ hPa}}$) (contour lines represented in black, with a spacing of 40 gpm) from 12 UTC on 21 May to 12 UTC on 28 May 2018.

Figure C6. (a–h) ERA5 reanalysis data for 350 hPa temperature ($T_{350 \text{ hPa}}$) (in °C, shading colours), and 350 hPa geopotential height ($Z_{350 \text{ hPa}}$) (contour lines represented in black, with a spacing of 40 gpm) from 12 UTC on 21 May to 12 UTC on 28 May 2018.

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Spatial-Temporal Variability of Hourly Precipitation Extremes in Portugal: Two Case Studies in Major Wine-Growing Regions

Figure C7. (a–h) ERA5 reanalysis data for 500 hPa temperature ($T_{500 \text{ hPa}}$) (in °C, shading colours), and 500 hPa geopotential height ($Z_{500 \text{ hPa}}$) (contour lines represented in black, with a spacing of 40 gpm) from 12 UTC on 21 May to 12 UTC on 28 May 2018.

Appendix D:

**Forecasting Heavy Precipitation in Portugal: AROME
Numerical Prediction Model Performance**

Table D1. List of the selected 105 surface weather stations (WS) in mainland Portugal, organised by region: code, weather station name, latitude (°N), longitude (°W) and altitude (meters above mean sea level). Stations marked with ‘#’ represent the selected surface weather stations to characterise the Douro winemaking region. Stations marked with ‘+’ represent the selected surface weather stations to characterise the Alentejo winemaking region.

Code	Weather Station name	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)	Altitude (m)
Northern Region				
531	Cabo Carvoeiro / Farol	39.361	-9.407	32
545	Porto - Pedras Rubras	41.232	-8.679	69
546	Porto - Serra do Pilar	41.139	-8.603	93
548	Coimbra / Aeródromo	40.158	-8.469	171
551	Viana do Castelo - Chafé	41.649	-8.805	48
559	Viseu / Aeródromo	40.726	-7.889	628
560	Viseu / Aeródromo	40.715	-7.896	636
568	Penhas Douradas / Observatório	40.411	-7.559	1380
570	Castelo Branco	39.839	-7.479	386
575	Bragança	41.804	-6.743	690
604	Vila Nova de Cerveira / Aeródromo	41.973	-8.676	34
605	Monção - Valinha	42.073	-8.381	80
606	Lamas de Mouro	42.043	-8.199	880
610	Viana do Castelo / Cidade	41.695	-8.830	18
611	Montalegre	41.823	-7.788	1005
612	Vinhais	41.843	-7.003	773
615	Ponte de Lima / Escola Agrícola	41.764	-8.571	40
616	Chaves / Aeródromo	41.725	-7.465	360
619	Cabril - S. Lourenço	41.710	-8.027	585
622	Braga - Merelim	41.576	-8.451	65
632	Mirandela	41.515	-7.191	250
633	Macedo de Cavaleiros - Izeda-Morais	41.568	-6.787	702
635	Miranda do Douro	41.499	-6.272	693
643	Paços de Ferreira	41.270	-8.380	–
649	Porto - S.Gens	41.184	-8.644	90
655	Pinhão	41.173	-7.549	130
657	Luzim	41.146	-8.249	250
666	Trancoso / Bandarra	40.781	-7.357	840
669	Arouca	40.927	-8.261	270
671	Figueira de Castelo Rodrigo - V.Torpim	40.830	-6.941	635
675	Viseu / Cidade	40.663	-7.904	443

Appendix D:

Forecasting Heavy Precipitation in Portugal: AROME Numerical Prediction Model Performance

Code	Weather Station name	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)	Altitude (m)
683	Guarda	40.529	-7.279	1020
685	Nelas	40.523	-7.855	425
686	Pampilhosa da Serra	40.146	-7.927	890
687	Covilhã	40.264	-7.482	482
690	Aldeia Souto - Quinta Lageosa	40.354	-7.389	468
697	Lousã - Aeródromo	40.144	-8.244	195
698	Fundão	40.141	-7.504	493
702	Aveiro / Universidade	40.635	-8.660	5
704	Dunas de Mira	40.446	-8.762	14
705	Anadia / Estação Vitivinícola da Bairrada	40.439	-8.440	45
707	Coimbra - Bencanta	40.213	-8.455	35
713	Figueira da Foz - Vila Verde	40.140	-8.806	4
716	Ansião	39.898	-8.410	405
718	Leiria / Aeródromo	39.781	-8.821	45
721	São Pedro de Moel	39.764	-9.031	40
724	Tomar - Vale Donas	39.592	-8.374	75
726	Alcobaça	39.548	-8.969	38
729	Rio Maior / ETAR	39.314	-8.924	69
800	Sabugal - Martim Rei	40.339	-7.037	858
803	Zebreira	39.850	-7.069	374
806	Proença-a-Nova - Moitas	39.729	-7.871	379
812	Alvega	39.461	-8.027	51
903	Porto - Massarelos	41.153	-8.626	74
566 (#)	Vila Real / Cidade	41.309	-7.741	481
567 (#)	Vila Real / Aeródromo	41.274	-7.717	561
571 (+)	Portalegre	39.294	-7.421	597
630 (#)	Cabeceiras de Basto	41.489	-7.980	350
637 (#)	Mogadouro	41.335	-6.726	644
644 (#)	Carrazêda de Ansiães	41.243	-7.299	715
654 (#)	Moncorvo	41.190	-7.019	600
663 (#)	Moimenta da Beira	40.986	-7.604	715
Southern Region				
533	Sagres / Quartel da Marinha	37.013	-8.949	25
535	Lisboa / Geofísico	38.719	-9.150	77
541	Sines - Monte Chãos	37.955	-8.838	103
554	Faro / Aeródromo	37.017	-7.972	8
577	Odemira - S. Teotónio	37.547	-8.729	76

Code	Weather Station name	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)	Altitude (m)
579	Lisboa - Gago Coutinho	38.766	-9.127	104
734	Santarém - Fonte Boa / Est. Zootécnica	39.201	-8.737	73
739	Torres Vedras - Dois Portos	39.044	-9.179	110
744	Coruche / Estação de Regadio (INIA)	38.942	-8.513	25
746	Santa Cruz / Aeródromo	39.126	-9.379	38
747	Colares	38.813	-9.460	25
750	Cabo da Roca	38.782	-9.498	142
762	Lisboa - Tapada da Ajuda	38.710	-9.183	62
765	Cabo Raso / Farol	38.709	-9.485	9
766	Barreiro - Lavradio	38.674	-9.048	6
767	Pegões	38.651	-8.635	64
770	Setúbal / Estação de Fruticultura	38.548	-8.891	35
773	Almada - Praia da Rainha	38.617	-9.213	7
776	Alcácer do Sal - Barrosinha	38.364	-8.482	29
788	Zambujeira	37.582	-8.743	67
789	Aljezur	37.325	-8.802	16
790	Foía	37.314	-8.596	902
826	Mora	38.941	-8.164	110
848	Portel - Oriola	38.318	-7.861	205
863	Mértola - Vale Formoso	37.758	-7.552	190
864	Castro Verde - Neves Corvo	37.577	-7.972	225
865	Alcoutim - Martim Longo	37.438	-7.769	290
866	Vila Real de S. António	37.187	-7.416	11
867	Castro Marim / Reserva Nacional do Sapat	37.230	-7.425	5
874	Albufeira	37.094	-8.262	–
878	Portimão / Aeródromo	37.147	-8.583	2
881	Olhão / EPPO	37.033	-7.821	7
883	Tavira	37.120	-7.620	2
557 (+)	Évora	38.572	-7.906	309
558 (+)	Évora / Aeródromo	38.537	-7.888	246
562 (+)	Beja	38.026	-7.867	246
783 (+)	Alvalade	37.947	-8.394	61
824 (+)	Avis - Benavila	39.107	-7.878	150
835 (+)	Elvas / Est. Melhoramento Plantas	38.890	-7.141	208
837 (+)	Estremoz - Techocas	38.862	-7.513	366
840 (+)	Reguengos - S. Pedro do Corval	38.485	-7.473	249
847 (+)	Viana do Alentejo	38.332	-8.046	202

Appendix D:Forecasting Heavy Precipitation in Portugal: AROME Numerical Prediction Model Performance

Code	Weather Station name	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)	Altitude (m)
851 (+)	Amareleja	38.201	-7.226	180

Table D2. Coordinates the Advanced Lightning Sensors (LS7002) and the TLP (Total Lightning Processor) system at IPMA headquarters in Lisbon.

Sensors	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)
Bragança	41.855	6.706
Braga	41.551	8.422
Castelo Branco	39.823	7.491
Santa Cruz	39.128	9.380
Olhão	37.025	7.840
Lisboa	38.776	9.126

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Table D3. Contingency tables for each region (Northern and Southern Region) for hourly precipitation totals and 3-hour accumulated precipitation (in parentheses, $\Delta t = 3h$) to the precipitation threshold $\geq 1, 10$ and 20 mm. This was according to the 12 UTC run from the previous day.

Prec ≥ 1 mm – Hourly ($\Delta t = 3h$)							
Northern Region				Southern Region			
	Observed				Observed		
Forecast	Yes	No	Total	Forecast	Yes	No	Total
Yes	15205 (34215)	33148 (46650)	48353 (80865)	Yes	3812 (10413)	14117 (24536)	17929 (34949)
No	3436 (4026)	285629 (300505)	289065 (304531)	No	1583 (2245)	236825 (260612)	238408 (262857)
Total	18641 (38241)	318777 (347155)	337418 (385396)	Total	5395 (12658)	250942 (285148)	256337 (297806)
Prec ≥ 10 mm – Hourly ($\Delta t = 3h$)							
Northern Region				Southern Region			
	Observed				Observed		
Forecast	Yes	No	Total	Forecast	Yes	No	Total
Yes	289 (4058)	3534 (16671)	3823 (20729)	Yes	82 (830)	1468 (6856)	1550 (7686)
No	382 (1261)	333213 (363406)	333595 (364667)	No	152 (498)	254635 (289622)	254787 (290120)
Total	671 (5319)	336747 (380077)	337418 (385396)	Total	234 (1328)	256103 (296478)	256337 (297806)
Prec ≥ 20 mm – Hourly ($\Delta t = 3h$)							
Northern Region				Southern Region			
	Observed				Observed		
Forecast	Yes	No	Total	Forecast	Yes	No	Total
Yes	13 (761)	408 (6910)	421 (7671)	Yes	4 (185)	203 (2830)	207 (3015)
No	56 (407)	336941 (377318)	336997 (377725)	No	40 (159)	256090 (294632)	256130 (294791)
Total	69 (1168)	337349 (384228)	337418 (385396)	Total	44 (344)	256293 (297462)	256337 (297806)

Figure D1. Spatial distribution of surface weather stations representative of Douro (dots represented in green) and Alentejo regions (dots represented in purple). Spatial distribution of five Advanced Lightning Sensors (ALS – LS7002) (represented in orange) and of the Total Lightning Processor (TLP) system (represented in olive).

Figure D2. Skill scores (a) POD, (b) HSS, (c) SEDS, and (d) FBIAS derived from contingency tables using 3 (represented in blue) and 6-hourly (represented in red) accumulated precipitation data, for each run, for the Northern Region and different precipitation thresholds.

Figure D3. Skill scores (a) POD, (b) HSS, (c) SEDS, and (d) FBIAS derived from contingency tables using 3 (represented in blue) and 6-hourly (represented in red) accumulated precipitation data, for each run, for the Southern Region and different precipitation thresholds.

Figure D4. The 75th percentile (represented in dashed line) and maximum (represented in filled line) chronological series over a 12-hour period in Douro region for bulk shear (BS, in $m s^{-1}$) between (a) 10 m and 400 hPa, (b) 10 m and 500 hPa, (c) 80 m and 400 hPa, (d) 80 m and 500 hPa, (e) 850 and 400 hPa, (f) 850 and 500 hPa, (g) 925 and 400 hPa, and (h) 925 and 500 hPa based on AROME forecasts started at 00 UTC on 27 May 2018 (R27_00, shown in red), 12 UTC on 27 May 2018 (R27_12, shown in blue) and 00 UTC on 28 May 2018 (R28_00, shown in green). The hourly distribution of lightning observations recorded in the Douro region is represented by bars. For each forecast step, the 75th percentile (p75th) and maxima (Max) values of the predictors are computed over the area marked in **Erro! A origem da referência não foi encontrada.**

Figure D5. 75th percentile (represented in dashed line) and maximum (represented in filled line) chronological series over a 17-hour period in Alentejo region for bulk shear (BS, in $m s^{-1}$) between (a) 10 m and 400 hPa, (b) 10 m and 500 hPa, (c) 80 m and 400 hPa, (d) 80 m and 500 hPa, (e) 850 and 400 hPa, (f) 850 and 500 hPa, (g) 925 and 400 hPa, and (h) 925 and 500 hPa, based on AROME forecasts started at 00 UTC on 13 September 2021 (R13_00, shown in red), 12 UTC on 13 September 2021 (R13_12, shown in blue) and 00 UTC on 14 September 2021 (R14_00, shown in green). The hourly distribution of lightning observations recorded in the Douro region is represented by bars. For each forecast step, the 75th percentile (p75th) and maxima (Max) values of the predictors are computed over the area marked in **Erro! A origem da referência não foi encontrada.**

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Figure D6. Spatial distribution of (a) observed precipitation (circles) and lightning observations (stars represented in green), and based on AROME forecasts started at: (b) 00 UTC on 27 May 2018 (R27_00), (c) 12 UTC on 27 May 2018 (R27_12) and (d) 00 UTC on 28 May 2018 (R28_00), valid for the period between 14 and 19 UTC on 28 May 2018 in the north-central region.

Figure D7. Spatial distribution of (a) observed precipitation (circles) and lightning observations (stars represented in green), and based on AROME forecasts started at: (b) 00 UTC on 13 September 2021 (R13_00), (c) 12 UTC on 13 September 2021 (R13_12) and (d) 00 UTC on 14 September 2021 (R14_00), valid for the period between 02 and 18 UTC on 14 September 2021 in the south-central region.

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Figure D8. Same as Figure D7, but valid for the period between 09 and 15 UTC on 14 September 2021.

Figure D9. Same as Figure D7, but valid for the period between 16 and 18 UTC on 14 September 2021.

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Figure D10. AROME forecast started at 12 UTC on 27 May 2018 (R27_12), valid between 14 UTC and 19 UTC on 28 May 2018, for the Douro wine region case study: (a) K-index (in °C), (b) Total-Totals index (TT-index, in °C), (c) potential instability (PI, in °C), and (d) bulk shear between 850 and 300 hPa (BS_{850-300 hPa}, in m s⁻¹).

Figure D11. AROME forecast started at 12 UTC on 13 September 2021 (R13_12), valid between 02 UTC and 08 UTC on 14 September 2021, for the south-central region: (a) K-index (in °C), (b) Total-Totals index (TT-index, in °C), (c) potential instability (PI, in °C), and (d) bulk shear between 850 and 300 hPa (BS_{850-300 hPa}, in m s⁻¹).

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Figure D12. Same as **Figure D11**, but valid for the period between 09 and 15 UTC on 14 September 2021.

Figure D13. Same as Figure D11, but valid for the period between 16 and 18 UTC on 14 September 2021.

Figure D14. (a) Vertical velocity at 600 hPa (VV600 hPa, in Pa s^{-1}) and lightning observations (stars represented in green), (b) zonal cross-section S1–QB of the vertical velocity (shading in Pa s^{-1}), equivalent potential temperature (θ_e , black contours in K, 2 K spacing), 0 °C isotherm (dark green line) and horizontal wind (wind barbs represented in black) based on AROME forecasts started at 12 UTC on 27 May 2018 (R27_12), valid between 12 UTC and 15 UTC on 28 May 2018.

Figure D15. Same as Figure D14, but valid for the period between 16 UTC and 19 UTC on 28 May 2018.

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Figure D16. Zonal cross-section S1–QB of the specific humidity (in g kg^{-1}) based on AROME forecasts started at 12 UTC on 27 May 2018 (R27_12), valid between 09 UTC and 21 UTC on 28 May 2018.

Figure D17. (a) Vertical velocity at 600 hPa (VV600 hPa, in Pa s⁻¹) and lightning observations (stars represented in green), (b) zonal cross-section S1-HE and (c) S2-HE of the vertical velocity (shading in Pa s⁻¹), equivalent potential temperature (θ_e , black contours in K, 2 K spacing), 0 °C isotherm (dark green line) and horizontal wind (wind barbs represented in black) based on AROME forecasts started at 12 UTC on 13 September 2021 (R13_12), valid between 02 UTC and 05 UTC on 14 September 2021.

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Figure D18. Same as **Figure D17**, but valid for the period between 06 UTC and 09 UTC on 14 September 2021.

Figure D19. Same as Figure D17, but valid for the period between 10 UTC and 13 UTC on 14 September 2021.

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Figure D20. Same as **Figure D17**, but valid for the period between 14 UTC and 17 UTC on 14 September 2021.

Figure D21. (a) Zonal cross-section S1–HE and (b) S2–HE of the specific humidity (in g kg^{-1}) based on AROME forecasts started at 12 UTC on 13 September 2021 (R13_12), valid between 02 UTC and 06 UTC on 14 September 2021.

Figure D22. Same as Figure D21, but valid for the period between 07 UTC and 11 UTC on 14 September 2021.

Figure D23. Same as Figure D21, but valid for the period between 12 UTC and 16 UTC on 14 September 2021.

Figure D24. Same as Figure D21, but valid for the period between 17 UTC and 18 UTC on 14 September 2021.

Appendix E:

**Performance of ECMWF Forecasts for Convective
Events Using Radar-Based and Multi-Source
Observations**

Table E1. List of the selected 42 surface weather stations (WS) in the southern region of mainland Portugal: code, weather station name, latitude ($^{\circ}$ N), longitude ($^{\circ}$ W) and altitude (meters above mean sea level).

Code	Weather Station name	Latitude ($^{\circ}$ N)	Longitude ($^{\circ}$ W)	Altitude (m)
533	Sagres / Quartel da Marinha	37.013	8.949	25
535	Lisboa / Geofísico	38.719	9.150	77
536	Lisboa / Aeroporto	38.789	9.135	121
550	Coruche Cruz do Leão	39.071	8.400	166
553	Loulé Cavalos do Caldeirão	37.304	7.953	587
554	Faro / Aeródromo	37.017	7.972	8
557	Évora	38.572	7.906	309
558	Évora / Aeródromo	38.537	7.888	246
562	Beja	38.026	7.867	246
577	Odemira - S. Teotónio	37.547	8.729	76
579	Lisboa - Gago Coutinho	38.766	9.127	104
580	Lisboa / Relógio	38.762	9.125	114
744	Coruche / Estação de Regadio (INIA)	38.942	8.513	25
758	Tiro/Alcochete	38.763	8.783	41
762	Lisboa - Tapada da Ajuda	38.710	9.183	62
766	Barreiro - Lavradio	38.674	9.048	6
767	Pegões	38.651	8.635	64
770	Setúbal / Estação de Fruticultura	38.548	8.891	35
773	Almada - Praia da Rainha	38.617	9.213	7
776	Alcácer do Sal - Barrosinha	38.364	8.482	29
783	Alvalade	37.947	8.394	61
788	Zambujeira	37.582	8.743	67
789	Aljezur	37.325	8.802	16
790	Foía	37.314	8.596	902
826	Mora	38.941	8.164	110
835	Elvas / Est. Melhoramento Plantas	38.890	7.141	208
837	Estremoz - Techocas	38.862	7.513	366
840	Reguengos - S. Pedro do Corval	38.485	7.473	249
842	Univ. Évora	38.525	8.017	265
846	Montemor-o-Novo	38.645	8.199	226
847	Viana do Alentejo	38.332	8.046	202
851	Amareleja	38.201	7.226	180

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Code	Weather Station name	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)	Altitude (m)
863	Mértola - Vale Formoso	37.758	7.552	190
864	Castro Verde - Neves Corvo	37.577	7.972	225
865	Alcoutim - Martim Longo	37.438	7.769	290
872	Loulé	37.130	8.065	68
874	Albufeira	37.094	8.262	109
878	Portimão / Aeródromo	37.147	8.583	2
879	Praia da Rocha	37.117	8.530	26
881	Olhão / EPPO	37.033	7.821	7
883	Tavira	37.120	7.620	2
9000	IPMA / Sede	38.775	9.126	95

Table E2. Coordinates of the Advanced Lightning Sensors (LS7002) and the TLP (Total Lightning Processor) system at IPMA headquarters in Lisbon.

Sensors	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)
Bragança	41.855	6.706
Braga	41.551	8.422
Castelo Branco	39.823	7.491
Santa Cruz	39.128	9.380
Olhão	37.025	7.840

Appendix E:

Performance of ECMWF Forecasts for Convective Events Using Radar-Based and Multi-Source Observations

Figure E1. Histograms of the relative distribution of the lightning events (coloured bars, in %) and corresponding cumulative frequency curve (black line), considering two thresholds of lightning density (DEA): **(a, b)** DEA ≥ 2 , and **(c, d)** DEA ≥ 10 . Panels on the left **(a, c)** present event classes based on the maximum RKDP (mm h⁻¹) within a radial distance of 10 km, whereas panels on the right **(b, d)** show event classes according to the IndexCON values. The total number of events considered (N) in each case is also outlined in each panel.

Figure E2. Histograms of the relative distribution of the lightning events (coloured bars, in %) and corresponding cumulative frequency curve (black line), considering two thresholds of lightning density (DEA): **(a, b)** DEA ≥ 2 , and **(c, d)** DEA ≥ 10 . Panels on the left **(a, c)** present event classes based on the maximum RKDP (mm h⁻¹) within a radial distance of 20 km, whereas panels on the right **(b, d)** show event classes according to the IndexCON values. The total number of events considered (N) in each case is also outlined in each panel.

Correspondence Ratio

Figure E3. Mean of correspondence ratio (CR) as a function of the ECMWF precipitation and the IndexCON thresholds for $RKDP \geq 15 \text{ mm h}^{-1}$. The columns distinguish between different matching time windows: (a) t , (b) $\Delta t = \pm 1 \text{ h}$, (c) $\Delta t = \pm 3 \text{ h}$ and (d) $\Delta t = \pm 6 \text{ h}$. The dark green line (with a closed circle) shows the CR mean between $ECMWF \cap RKDP$. For the IndexCON CRs: $IndexCON \cap (RKDP \cup DEA)$ (brown line with a square), $IndexCON \cap DEA$ (beige line with a \times marker) and $IndexCON \cap RKDP$ (orange line with a triangle).

Figure E4. Boxplots of the CR between ECMWF precipitation and IndexCON thresholds as a function of the minimum threshold intensity in RKDP and lightning density: (a) $ECMWF \cap RKDP \geq 10$ mm h⁻¹; (b) $IndexCON \cap (RKDP \geq 10$ mm h⁻¹ \cup $DEA \geq 2$); (c) $IndexCON \cap RKDP \geq 10$ mm h⁻¹; and (d) $IndexCON \cap DEA \geq 2$. Within each group, four temporal variants are shown: coincident events (t), and symmetric windowing ($\Delta t = \pm 1$ h and $\Delta t = \pm 3$ h). Boxplots display the median (coloured horizontal line), the interquartile range (box), the whiskers, and the mean (black cross).

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Performance of ECMWF Forecasts for Convective Events Using Radar-Based and Multi-Source Observations

Figure E5. Boxplots of the CR between ECMWF precipitation and IndexCON thresholds as a function of the minimum threshold intensity in RKDP and lightning density: (a) $\text{ECMWF} \cap \text{RKDP} \geq 15 \text{ mm h}^{-1}$; (b) $\text{IndexCON} \cap (\text{RKDP} \geq 15 \text{ mm h}^{-1} \cup \text{DEA} \geq 2)$; (c) $\text{IndexCON} \cap \text{RKDP} \geq 15 \text{ mm h}^{-1}$; and (d) $\text{IndexCON} \cap \text{DEA} \geq 2$. Within each group, four temporal variants are shown: coincident events (t), and symmetric windowing ($\Delta t = \pm 1$ h and $\Delta t = \pm 3$ h). Boxplots display the median (coloured horizontal line), the interquartile range (box), the whiskers, and the mean (black cross).

Figure E6. Mean of correspondence ratio (CR) is shown as a function of the (a) ECMWF precipitation and (b) the IndexCON thresholds for RKDP ≥ 10 (blue line with a closed circle), ≥ 15 (violet line with a square), and ≥ 17 mm h⁻¹ (red line with a triangle), considering the time window of the $\Delta t = \pm 1$ h.